

A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF THE WORKS OF RUSSIAN HISTORIANS COVERING THE ACTIVITIES OF LOCAL RULERS OF CENTRAL ASIA IN THE FIGHT AGAINST THE INVASION OF THE ARAB CALIPHATE IN THE 7TH-8TH CENTURIES.

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15852156>

Annotatsiya

Rus tarixchilarida Askajuvar va Chag'on bilan bir odam ekanligini ta'kidlagan. Arab xalifaligi qo'shinlarining Sug'd va Farg'ona vodiysiga qilgan yurishlari. Xorazm tangalari va mahalliy hukumdorlar tarixi. Yazdigardning arablar istilosidan Farg'onaga qochishi va Xurosonga qaytishi.

Kalit so'zlar: V.V.Bartold, A.N.Bernshtam, B.I.Vaynberg, O.N.Smirnova, Yazdigird III, 644-704 rr.

Annotation

Russian historians claim that he is the same person as Askajuvar and Chagan. The campaigns of the Arab Caliphate troops to Sughd and the Fergana Valley. The history of Khorezm coins and local rulers. Yazdighart's escape from the Arab invasion to Fergana and his return to Khorasan...

Key words: V. V. Bartold, A. N. Bernshtam, B. I. Weinberg, O. N. Smirnova, Yazdigird III, 644-704 yy.

Аннотация

Русские историки утверждают, что он одно лицо с Аскаджуваром и Чаганом. Походы войск Арабского халифата в Согд и Ферганскую долину. История монет Хорезма и местных правителей. Бегство Йездигарта от арабского нашествия в Фергану и его возвращение в Хорасан.

Ключевые слова: В. В. Бартольд, А. Н. Бернштам, Б. И. Вайнберг, О. Н. Смирнова, Йездигирд III, 644-704 гг.

After the collapse of the Soviet Union and the formation of independent states, the science of history developed to varying degrees. In Tajikistan, scientific research of various content and levels dedicated to the Arab conquest period was written and defended. Although most of them were defended in Tajikistan, all of them received the degrees of candidate of sciences and doctor of sciences by the decisions of the Higher Attestation Commission of the Russian Federation.

In 2010, Abdunazar Khaqnazarov defended his doctoral dissertation entitled "The Struggle of the Tajik People against the Arab Caliphate". The

research consists of 4 chapters. This dissertation discusses the formation of the Islamic religion, The establishment of the Muslim state, the conquest of Iran, the end of the Sassanid dynasty, the occupation of Khorasan and Transoxiana, popular movements against the Umayyad and Abbasid Caliphates, the establishment of the Samanid state, and other issues are covered. Some information about the activities of Gurak and Divashtich is recorded.¹

Under the scientific supervision of Abdunazar Khaqnazarov, who received his doctorate in 2010, Radjabov Saidnigmon Mulodjanovich will defend his candidate's dissertation on the topic "The Struggle of the Peoples of Maverannahr and Khorasan for Independence (VII - first half of the VIII century)". The struggle of the peoples of Maverannahr and Khorasan against the Arab invaders in the VII-VIII centuries is a very complex historical period: the resistance of the inhabitants of Maverannahr and Khorasan to the Arab invaders, their struggle for freedom and independence, and information about some local leaders in it are recorded.²

The scientific works belonging to the second group are also extensive in terms of time and geography. Most Russian historians, in their works devoted to the history of Central Asia, briefly touched upon the history of the activities of local rulers in the struggle against the Arab Caliphate invasion in the 7th-8th centuries. Among the major studies related to some aspects of the topic under study during the Russian Empire and the Soviet period, we can include the works of V.V. Bartold, A.N. Bernshtam, B.A. Litvinsky, B.G. Gafurov, H. Ne'matov, T. Kadyrova, R. Nabiyev, O.I. Smirnova, Sh. Kamoliddinov, S.G. Klyashtorniy. Since the main focus of these works is not the history of the activities of local rulers in the struggle against the Arab Caliphate invasion in the 7th-8th centuries, they contain only brief information on the topic we have chosen.

Among the scientific studies included in the second group, the works of the famous orientalist V.V. Bartold stand out for their scientific value and maximum use of sources. The author did not conduct a separate study on the history of the activities of local rulers in the fight against the invasion of the Arab Caliphate in the 7th-8th centuries. However, in his works dedicated to the history of Central Asia, he left some notes and expressed his views on this issue.

The section entitled "Central Asia until the 12th century" of V.V. Bartold's work "Turkestan in the Age of the Mongol Invasion" ("Central Asia until the 12th

¹ Хакназаров А. Борьба таджикского народа против арабского халифата диссертация на соискание ученой степени доктора исторических наук. – Душанбе, 2010. – С. 42-250.

² Раджабов С.М. Борьба народов Мавераннахра и Хорасана за независимость (VII – первая половина VIII вв.). Диссертация на соискание ученой степени кандидата исторических наук. – Душанбе, 2010. – С. 21-132.

century”) contains information about the early medieval historical geography of the Fergana Valley, as well as several Arab invasions of Central Asia and the Fergana Valley.³

During the Soviet era, the historian T. Kadyrova conducted serious research on the history of Central Asia in the 8th-9th centuries, and her monograph “From the history of peasant uprisings in Khorasan and Maverannahr in the early 8th-9th centuries” is of great importance. It provides important information about the activities of local rulers in the fight against the invasion of the Arab Caliphate in the 7th-8th centuries. Although the researcher did not set herself the goal of studying the history of the Fergana Valley, in the process of describing the popular movements of the 8th century, she cites the attitude of the Fergana people to it. In her work, the author mainly covers the popular movements in administrative units that were directly incorporated into the caliphate. Since Fergana was governed by a local dynasty at that time, the fight against the Arabs in the valley was carried out by representatives of this dynasty. That is probably why this monograph, written during the Soviet era, does not cover the history of the struggle against the Arabs in the Fergana Valley very well.

Another study related to our topic is the treatise “Ancient Fergana (Popular Scientific Essay)” by A.N. Bernshtam. The treatise is a preliminary study describing the history of the Fergana Valley from ancient times to the Timurids. The work does not devote any space to the history of the Hephthalite period. It tells about the Turkish Khaganate, the conquest of the Arab Caliphate and the Samanid period in many cases using archaeological materials. In the part of the work on the Turkish Khaganate, the Arab Caliphate and the Samanid period, first of all, the history of the valley is briefly described, and then its archaeological monuments of this period are analyzed. In the work, where the history of the valley is written with information taken from the works of medieval historians, almost no references are made to their works.

Both books of the monograph “Tajiks” (Tajiks), published by G. Gafurov, contain significant information about the history of the activities of local rulers in the fight against the invasion of the Arab Caliphate in the 7th-8th centuries. The book consists of two parts, the first of which covers the history of Central Asia from ancient times to the early Middle Ages. The second part of the work provides general information about the campaigns of the Arab Caliphate troops

³ Бартольд В. Туркестан в эпоху монгольского нашествия. Соч. 1 – Москва: Восточная литература, 1963. – С. 225 (keyingi o‘rinlarda – Бартольд В. Туркестан...).

in Sughd and the Fergana Valley, the activities of Gurak, Divashtich and the Fergana Tsar Alutar⁴.

The researcher B.I. Weinberg was known for his numismatic research during the Soviet period, and in his monograph “Монеты древнего Хорезма” he tried to write about the ancient Khorezm coins and through them the history of local rulers. Coins of the 7th-8th centuries and earlier periods have been studied in depth by a number of researchers. Although a ruler named Chag'on, who ruled at the beginning of this century, is mentioned in Arabic sources, on coins minted during this period he is mentioned under the name Askarjuvar. B.I. Weinberg emphasized in his monograph that Askajūvar and Chag'on were the same person. However, an analysis of written sources shows that Chag'on and Askarjuvar were separate rulers. The coins that are said to belong to Askajūvar are coins of the “G 11a” type in V. I. Weinberg's research, and on the obverse of the coin there is an image of a crowned ruler without a beard.⁵

The study “Essays from the History of Sogd” (Essays from the History of Sogd) by O.N. Smirnova, although not directly devoted to the history of the Fergana Valley, contains interesting insights into the history of the valley. For example, the work includes a chronological table of the rulers who ruled Fergana, along with other regions of Central Asia.⁶

G. Goibov's monograph "Early Campaigns of the Arabs in Central Asia (644-704 gg.)" (The First Campaigns of the Arabs in Central Asia) tells about the invasion of the Arab Caliphate in Fergana, as well as in other regions of Central Asia. G. Goipov's opinion that the information about the last ruler of the Sassanids, Yazdigird III (632-652), Yazdigird's escape from the Arab invasion to Fergana and his return to Khorasan, actually belongs to his son Feruz is one of the noteworthy aspects of the research. G. Goibov's thesis "To the Chronology of the Bukhara Rulers of the Arab Conquest (VII-VIII centuries)" provides a list of representatives of the Bukhara dynasty, which is the basis for most Internet sites today⁷.

⁴ Гафуров Б.Г. Таджики. Кн I. – 480 с.

⁵ Вайнберг Б.И. Монеты древнего Хорезма. – М.: “Наука”, 1977. – С. 198.; Ismailov Sh. VIII-XIII asrlarda Xorazmshohlar tangalari. Tarix fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD) ilmiy darajasini olish uchun yozilgan dissertatsiyasi avtoreferati. Urganch, 2024. – B. 14.

⁶ Смирнова О.И. Очерки из истории Согда. – С. 255.

⁷ Гоибов Г. К хронологии бухарских правителей арабского завоевания (VII—VIII вв.) // Ответственные редакторы: Б. И. Искандаров, В. М. Массон, Н. Н. Негматов. Раннесредневековая культура Средней Азии и Казахстана (Тезисы Всесоюзной научной конференции в г. Пенджикенте Таджикской ССР, 26–31 августа 1977 г.). Душанбе: Дониш, 1977. – С. 177–178.

References:

1. Хакназаров А. Борьба таджикского народа против арабского халифата диссертация на соискание ученой степени доктора исторических наук. – Душанбе, 2010. – С. 42-250.
2. Раджабов С.М. Борьба народов Мавераннахр и Хорасана за независимость (VII – первая половина VIII вв.). Диссертация на соискание ученой степени кандидата исторических наук. – Душанбе, 2010. – С. 21-132.
3. Бартольд В. Туркестан в эпоху монгольского нашествия. Соч. 1 – Москва: Восточная литература, 1963. – С. 225 (keyingi o'rinlarda – Бартольд В. Туркестан...)
4. Гафуров Б.Г. Таджики. Кн I. – 480 с.
5. Вайнберг Б.И. Монеты древнего Хорезма. – М.: “Наука”, 1977. – С. 198.; Ismailov Sh. VIII-XIII asrlarda Xorazmshohlar tangalari. Tarix fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD) ilmiy darajasini olish uchun yozilgan dissertatsiyasi avtoreferati. Urganch, 2024. – B. 14.
6. Смирнова О.И. Очерки из истории Согда. – С. 255.
7. Гоибов Г. К хронологии бухарских правителей арабского завоевания (VII—VIII вв.) // Ответственные редакторы: Б. И. Искандаров, В. М. Массон, Н. Н. Негматов. Раннесредневековая культура Средней Азии и Казахстана (Тезисы Всесоюзной научной конференции в г. Пенджикенте Таджикской ССР, 26–31 августа 1977 г.). – Душанбе: Дониш, 1977. – С. 177–178.

